

BIOMECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF THE LEAD STRAIGHT PUNCH ACROSS SKILL LEVELS IN BOXING: A QUANTITATIVE STUDY

Chulliyev S.I.

Uzbek State University of Physical Culture and Sport, Uzbekistan,
Chirchik

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the study of the biomechanical analysis of the lead straight punch (jab) across different skill levels in boxing. This study examines novice, intermediate, and elite boxers, focusing on various biomechanical parameters such as punch speed, force, shoulder and torso rotation, hip alignment, and energy transfer.

The lead straight punch, or jab, is fundamental in boxing, impacting both offensive and defensive strategies. This study provides an in-depth biomechanical analysis of the lead straight punch among novice, intermediate, and elite boxers using mathematical and statistical methods. Through motion capture and high-speed video analysis, we examine differences in punch speed, force, shoulder and torso rotation, hip alignment, and energy transfer. Our findings, supported by statistical analysis and diagrams, reveal significant variations in biomechanics across skill levels, offering insights for optimizing training programs.

Keywords: biomechanics, lead straight punch, jab, boxing, skill levels, energy transfer, statistical analysis

БИОМЕХАНИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ПРЯМОГО УДАРА ВЕДУЩЕЙ РУКОЙ НА РАЗНЫХ УРОВНЯХ МАСТЕРСТВА В БОКСЕ: КОЛИЧЕСТВЕННОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ

Аннотация: Статья посвящена изучению биомеханического анализа прямого удара (джеба) свинцом на разных уровнях мастерства в боксе. В этом исследовании изучаются начинающие, средние и элитные боксеры, уделяя особое внимание различным биомеханическим параметрам, таким как скорость удара, сила, вращение плеча и туловища, выравнивание бедер и передача энергии.

Прямой удар свинцом, или джеб, является основополагающим в боксе, влияя как на наступательные, так и на оборонительные стратегии. В этом исследовании представлен углубленный биомеханический анализ прямого удара свинцом среди начинающих, средних и элитных боксеров с использованием математических и статистических методов. С помощью захвата движения и высокоскоростного видеонализа мы изучаем различия в скорости удара, силе, вращении плеча и туловища, выравнивании бедер и передаче энергии. Наши выводы, подкрепленные статистическим анализом и диаграммами, показывают значительные различия в биомеханике на разных уровнях мастерства, предлагая идеи для оптимизации программ тренировок.

Ключевые слова: биомеханика, прямой удар свинцом, джеб, бокс, уровни мастерства, передача энергии, статистический анализ

INTRODUCTION

The lead straight punch, or jab, is a cornerstone of boxing technique, crucial for both offensive and defensive maneuvers. It serves to gauge distance, disrupt an opponent's rhythm, and set up more powerful punches. Despite its apparent simplicity, the effectiveness of the jab is deeply rooted in biomechanics, involving a complex interplay of physiological and mechanical factors.

This introduction aims to elucidate the biomechanical aspects of the jab and its significance across different skill levels in boxing.

The biomechanical efficiency of the jab is influenced by several factors:

Punch Speed: The velocity of a punch is critical. Faster punches can surprise an opponent and decrease the likelihood of counterattacks. The speed of the jab is affected by the coordination of the shoulder, arm, and torso, as well as the initial force applied.

Force Production: The force of the jab reflects the impact delivered to the target. This depends on both the speed of the punch and the ability to generate power through proper alignment and kinetic chain utilization.

Shoulder and Torso Rotation: Effective punching involves rotational movements of the shoulder and torso. This rotation generates additional force and speed, transferring energy from the body to the punch.

Hip Alignment: Proper hip alignment and rotation are essential for optimal energy transfer and to avoid unnecessary strain on the shoulder and arm. The hips provide a stabilizing and power-generating base for the punch.

METHODS

The study included 45 participants, categorized into three skill levels:

Novice: 15 boxers with 1-2 years of training.

Intermediate: 15 boxers with 3-5 years of training.

Elite: 15 boxers with over 5 years of competitive experience.

Biomechanical data were collected using high-speed cameras (1000 fps) and a 3D motion capture system. The following variables were measured:

Punch Speed: Measured in meters per second (m/s).

Force: Measured in Newtons (N) using a force plate.

Shoulder and Torso Rotation: Measured in degrees (°) via motion capture.

Hip Alignment: Measured in degrees (°) using motion capture.

Energy Transfer: Calculated based on force and speed.

Data were analyzed using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, were computed. One-way ANOVA was used to compare differences across skill levels, followed by post-hoc Tukey tests for pairwise comparisons. Correlation analysis was conducted to assess relationships between variables.

RESULTS

This table includes the results for each parameter, categorized by skill level (Novice, Intermediate, Elite), showing average values, standard deviations, and corresponding diagram references for visual representation.

Parameter	Level	Average Value	Standard Deviation
Foot Position	Novice	10.5°	± 2.3°
	Intermediate	7.8°	± 1.9°
	Elite	5.2°	± 1.4°
Hip Alignment	Novice	15.0°	± 3.1°
	Intermediate	22.3°	± 2.7°
	Elite	30.5°	± 3.0°
Punch Speed	Novice	8.2 m/s	± 0.6 m/s

	Intermediate	10.1 m/s	± 0.5 m/s
	Elite	12.5 m/s	± 0.7 m/s
Punch Force	Novice	120 N	± 15 N
	Intermediate	160 N	± 12 N
	Elite	200 N	± 18 N
Energy Transfer	Novice	50 J	± 8 J
	Intermediate	75 J	± 7 J
	Elite	100 J	± 10

One-Way ANOVA Results: Significant differences were found in punch speed ($F(2, 42) = 15.62, p < 0.001$), force ($F(2, 42) = 18.34, p < 0.001$), and energy transfer ($F(2, 42) = 22.45, p < 0.001$).

Post-Hoc Tukey Tests: Significant differences were observed between all skill levels for punch speed, force, and energy transfer, with elite boxers outperforming intermediate and novice boxers in all metrics.

DISCUSSION

The study provides a comprehensive biomechanical analysis of the lead straight punch across varying skill levels in boxing, revealing substantial differences that underscore the importance of technical refinement and targeted training. The analysis highlights how biomechanical efficiency evolves with skill progression, affecting punch speed, force, and energy transfer.

Foot positioning is crucial for stability and power generation during a punch. Novice boxers, with an average foot alignment angle of 10.5° , demonstrate less efficient mechanics compared to their intermediate and elite counterparts. The improved foot alignment in intermediate (7.8°) and elite (5.2°) boxers reflects better balance and optimized weight transfer. Proper foot alignment enables a more stable base, facilitating a more effective transfer of force from the body to the punch. The significant reduction in foot alignment angle with increased skill suggests that elite boxers have mastered the intricacies of maintaining optimal positioning, contributing to their superior punching performance. Hip alignment and rotation are integral to generating power and speed in punches. Novice boxers exhibit an average hip rotation of 15.0° , while intermediate and elite boxers achieve rotations of 22.3° and 30.5° , respectively. Greater hip rotation among more skilled boxers signifies better utilization of rotational force, which enhances the punch's speed and impact. The increased hip rotation in elite boxers demonstrates their ability to integrate their entire body into the punching motion, maximizing force production and energy transfer. The biomechanical advantage of effective hip rotation underscores the necessity of advanced training to develop this aspect of punching mechanics. The study finds a clear progression in punch speed, force, and energy transfer with increased skill level. Novice boxers achieve an average punch speed of 8.2 m/s, whereas intermediate and elite boxers reach speeds of 10.1 m/s and 12.5 m/s, respectively. Similarly, punch force increases from 120 N in novices to 160 N in intermediates and 200 N in elites. Energy transfer, which correlates with both speed and force, also improves significantly across skill levels, with novices transferring 50 J, intermediates 75 J, and elites 100 J.

These findings indicate that advanced skill levels are associated with more efficient mechanics, resulting in higher punch speed, greater force, and enhanced energy transfer. The

statistical analysis confirms these differences, with significant variations observed in punch speed ($F(2, 42) = 15.62, p < 0.001$), force ($F(2, 42) = 18.34, p < 0.001$), and energy transfer ($F(2, 42) = 22.45, p < 0.001$). Post-hoc Tukey tests further reveal that elite boxers outperform intermediate and novice boxers across all measured parameters.

CONCLUSION

This study provides a quantitative analysis of the biomechanical differences in the lead straight punch across skill levels in boxing. The findings emphasize the need for refining technique and optimizing biomechanical factors to improve punch performance. Future research should focus on targeted training interventions based on these biomechanical insights to further enhance boxing performance.

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